

H2020-SC5-01-2017

MED-GOLD

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **G**rape, **O**Live and **D**urum wheat food systems

Deliverable 6.7

Summary of dissemination and communication activities n. 1

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Disclaimer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The MED-GOLD project, which aims to demonstrate the proof-of-concept on how climate services can make European agriculture and food systems more competitive, resilient and efficient through three case studies in the olive, grape and durum wheat sectors, started the first of December 2017. After one year running, several activities have been performed on developing and implementing the appropriate dissemination and communication strategy that contribute towards the promotion of the project' results at European and international level.

The dissemination and communication work tries to maximize the impact of the project' results through different channels and target audiences, as it is described on the MED-GOLD deliverable D7.1 "Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD. 2]. This deliverable synthetises all the communication and disseminations activities performed during this first year.

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (GA, Part B Table 1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot climate services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	X
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	X

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE

A comprehensive and communal strategy on communication, dissemination and exploitation of the MED-GOLD project is required for a wide adoption of the project by the different target audiences. At this stage of the project, most of the work has been concentrated on defining and designing the core tools and technologies to be developed.

This document, as it is established on the MED-GOLD grant agreement, collects all contributions performed by the partners through the different tasks that have been carried out during the first year of the project, either on setting the corresponding channels or disseminating the project characteristics and advances. This initial description of C&D activities for the period M1-M12 has been extended to M18.

1.2. SCOPE

The scope of this deliverable is to present a yearly report related to the dissemination and communication activities performed by project partners, either on a collaborative approach or on their individual active roles. Communication and dissemination objectives and strategy performed is described as a summary of the activities that were undertaken on the reporting period.

To ensure that all communication and dissemination (C&D) activities have been properly logged, we employed the procedure described on deliverable D7.1 “Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan [RD. 2] and MED-GOLD Quality Plan [RD. 3]. In this way, all the activities were centralised in a spreadsheet that forms the basis of this report.

1.3. DEFINITIONS AND ACRONYMS

1.3.1. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-1 Definitions

Concept / Term	Definition
Communication	Strategic and targeted measures for promoting the results to a multitude of audiences
Dissemination	Public disclosure of the results by an appropriate communication channel.
Exploitation	Use of the results during and after the project's implementation. It can be for commercial purposes, improving policies and tackling economic and societal problems.

1.3.2. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
%	Percentage
ACIBEV	Association of wines and spirits of Portugal
ADVID	Association for the Development of Viticulture in the Douro Region
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
DSS	Decision Support System
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EGU	European Geosciences Union
IT	Italy
JPI	Joint Programming Initiative
GA	Grant Agreement

Acronym	Definition
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Public
GR	Greece
PR	Professional public
PT	Portugal
SP	Spain
WMO	World Meteorological Organization

2. REFERENCES

2.1. REFERENCE DOCUMENTS

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Table 2-1 Reference Documents

Ref.	Title	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD Grant Agreement	2017
[RD.2]	Deliverable 7.1. MED-GOLD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan	2018
[RD.3]	MED-GOLD Quality Plan	2018
[RD.4]	Deliverable 6.1. Climate related Initiatives Interactions Report 1	2018
[RD.5]	Milestone 2. MED-GOLD community developed	2018
[RD.6]	Milestone 3. Report on the MED-GOLD mailing list	2018
[RD.7]	Deliverable 6.8 Launch of external website	2018

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORTING PERIOD

Within the MED-GOLD Grant Agreement, different objectives and tasks related to communication and dissemination were established, especially in Work Package 6 “Communication and exploitation of the MED-GOLD value chain” [RD.1]. Deliverable 7.1, “MED-GOLD Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Management Plan” [RD.2], describes the development and implementation of the appropriate dissemination, communication strategy and related activities.

Responsibilities has been defined to ensure that each partner contribute to this strategy and a monitoring system has been implemented to realize of all the activities performed, detect opportunities and analyze weakness.

Different objectives have been reached during the first year of the project:

- Design and creation of the corporate identity of the project (logo, project template for presentation, newsletter, deliverables, etc.);
- Design and launch of the MED-GOLD website;
- Launch of MED-GOLD on the social networks (twitter);
- Identify and organize stakeholders groups;
- Identify, organize and enhance collaboration with other similar initiatives related to climate services;
- Promote the project on the press and media;

4. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND ACTIVITIES

Summary of the channels defined and implemented and the C&D activities performed during the first year (M1-M12).

4.1. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATIONS CHANNELS

The channels described in this section are the means through which the project's main messages can be transmitted and communicated outside the consortium.

A common corporate identify design has been the first stage in order to advance. This task was completed in collaboration with [Formicablu](#), a science communication agency. A logo has been designed and different templates for C&D materials. Figure 4-1 shows the selected MED-GOLD logo.

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-1. **MED-GOLD logos: initial draft (a) and final version (b)**

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-2. **MED-GOLD infographic poster**

4.1.1. MED-GOLD WEBSITE

The MED-GOLD website (www.med-gold.eu) was launched the week before the project's kick-off meeting (M1). This first version (Figure 4-3) was designed to disseminate the on-going activities of the project and to be the gateway for the engagement of stakeholders in the MED-GOLD community.

On M3 (February 2018), as it is described in D6.8 “launch of external website”, the MED-GOLD website was officially made public. Each section was available in English, Spanish, Italian, Portuguese French and Greek [RD.7]:

- Partners section: all members of the consortium are shown with direct links to the home page of each institution.
- Media section: pictures from the main events (meetings, external conferences, workshops, interviews...) were periodically added and updated.
- Contacts section: all the possible ways to connect with MED-GOLD are reported.

This first release of the official website aimed at being a first stopping place for people who will interact with the project and possibly become part of the MED-GOLD community.

In October 2018, the website was updated confirming the visual identity of the project (Figure 4-4). Moreover, new sections were included:

- Homepage including latest news, goals, invitation to participate in the discussion forum (MS4), discover the services for the three sectors and upcoming events;
- Project: describing the project storyline and the issues that will be addressed, climate services definition, workplan, partners and related projects;
- Documents: space for sharing deliverables, publications and policy briefs;
- Climate services: description of the general scope, the European roadmap for this type of services and the expectations for the three use cases of MED-GOLD. Also, name and email contacts for members of the teams working on MED-GOLD climate service development are included, with the first two contacts for each sector being the co-leaders of the related case study;
- Case studies: short description of the services that will be developed for the three sectors;
- Media: interviews, webinars, etc.
- Events & news: space in which MED-GOLD news and past and upcoming events are published;
- Internal area: access to MED-GOLD wiki for partners;
- Participate: online discussion site where those members of the MED-GOLD community can hold conversations related to the different categories such as: MED-GOLD community, Grapes-Wine sector, Olives-Olive oil sector, Durum wheat-Pasta sector and Agriculture in general since relevant stakeholders from other sectors might be interested on project results and replicability. More information about MED-GOLD community on MS 2 [RD. 5].

It should be noted that all forms and interactions with participants through the website has been designed taking into account the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (“GDPR”) related to data protection and privacy for all individuals within the European Union and the European Economic Area.

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda

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Latest news

MED-GOLD european project on climate threats to the agricultural sector

November 5th, 2018

Portugal, Spain and Italy are part of a project funded by the European Union in [...]

MED-GOLD workshop on olive at DCOOP

July 30th, 2018

The MED-GOLD olive/olive oil workshop was held on June 12 at the Dcoop facilities in [...]

MED-GOLD workshop on durum wheat at HORTA Ltd

May 29th, 2018

Prior to developing climate services tailored at the durum wheat sector, it is critical to [...]

Goals

MED-GOLD will develop novel pilot climate services focusing on three staples of the Mediterranean food system: Grape, olive and durum wheat.

The long-term objective of MED-GOLD is to make European agriculture and food systems more resilient, sustainable and efficient in the face of climate change, by using climate services to minimize climate driven risks/costs and seize opportunities for added value.

Participate

MED-GOLD is an inclusive project, seeking the contribution and active participation of experts and stakeholders to co-design the most effective climate services.

Reach out and share your knowledge with our community, we will keep you updated and you will be able to join our activities and our online discussion forum.

[Join the discussion forum](#)

Contacts

med-gold.project@enea.it

Follow us

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Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-4. **MED-GOLD homepage**

The main statistics of the MED-GOLD website since google analytics tracking was deployed (February 2019) are exposed on Figure 4-5. Until the 28th May of 21019, 1326 users were visiting MED-GOLD website. The 6 main countries were 28% from United States, 19% from Italy, 9% from Portugal, 7% Spain, 6% United Kingdom and 4% from Greece where more than 50% of the users are less than 34 years old.

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-5. **MED-GOLD visitor's distribution by country.**

4.1.2. MED-GOLD MAILING LISTS

As it was defined on Work Package 5 “Engaging, validating and exploiting the pilot services with the MED-GOLD community”, during task 5.1 “Developing the MED-GOLD community”, lists of contacts, initiatives, stakeholders and relevant actors on the three different sectors but also at climate service level (researcher, providers, commercial, etc.) have been compiled.

The University of Leeds, in collaboration with all partners, has sent (in two rounds done on August and September, respectively) a total of 683 introductory emails together with a project information sheet (Figure 4-5) to invite stakeholders and random European organization operating in the sectors of interest to join the MED-GOLD community. Once registered via the online user forum, they would receive periodic bulletins, participate in online surveys and be invited to webinars and other events related to the project. Moreover, 24 introductory phone calls have been made with policy markers (several European Ministries of Agriculture and public agencies)

As expected a cascade effect has occurred in which relevant stakeholders such as ADVID and ACIBEV, linked to the grape/wine sector, has also redirected the MED-GOLD' introductory email over 1000 people in Portugal who may be interested.

As a resulted of this first recruitment campaign, a total of 58 people have registered as MED-GOLD community members.

A more targeted approach is expected to be undertaken in the next weeks to have more of an impact effect and increase the number of members in an exponential way.

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-7. **MED-GOLD twitter**

4.1.4. MED-GOLD BROCHURE

Based on the original design of the information sheet (Figure 4-5), a brochure was designed in order to have an informative document which can be also used for advertising and engagement of stakeholders in the MED-GOLD community. This brochure is shown in Figure 4-7.

As a first round, one thousand copies have been shared within partners to assist with dissemination of the project.

MED-GOLD EXPECTED IMPACT

1. Involve users in the design, development, test, and evaluation of the added value of pilot climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat
2. Refine, validate, and upscale pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive / oil, grape / wine and durum wheat / pasta.
3. Ensure replicability of climate services for other crops / climates (e.g., coffee) and link with global policy-making
4. Implement a comprehensive communication and market plan to enhance uptake for MED-GOLD climate services
5. Build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making

Talk to our climate experts
in the MED-GOLD user forum:

med_gold.eu/forum

CONSORTIUM PARTNERS

GET INVOLVED

med-gold.eu/registration

Participate in our surveys, forum and workshop for the co-design of climate services for Mediterranean grapes/wine, olives/olive oil and durum wheat/pasta.

MED-GOLD

www.med-gold.eu
[@medgold_h2020](https://twitter.com/medgold_h2020)
[med-gold.project@enea.it](https://www.facebook.com/med-gold.project@enea.it)

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional Mediterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems

SHARE NEEDS
DISCUSS OPTIONS
VALIDATE SERVICES
BETHE FUTURE

MED-GOLD

MED-GOLD has received funds for the years 2017-2021 from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 776467

GRAPE/ WINE

Wine is produced all over the globe, but Europe still retains its traditional leadership role in winemaking - accounting for around 60% of the world's output - with Italy, France and Spain being by far the major producers.

MED-GOLD will formulate the best seasonal probabilistic predictions of extreme and biological climate indices at Mediterranean and site specific spatial scales, to allow for efficient pest and operational management strategies.

The climate service will support farmers in addressing issues like:

- How many protection treatments are expected for the upcoming season?
- What variety / rootstock / clone will I need in my area for the next 30 years?

OLIVE/ OLIVE OIL

The Olea europaea, or olive tree, has been part of the Mediterranean landscape for millennia, to the point that the unmistakable squat shape of this evergreen tree has become a symbol of the Mediterranean vegetation.

MED-GOLD will integrate models capable of predicting pest dynamics and fruit infestation by the olive fly (*Bactrocera oleae*), so to provide sensible information to support the best management and reduce agricultural costs by addressing issues like:

- When and where is olive fly pest expected in my area during the next season?
- Which new pests will I have to fight against during the next ten years?
- What will be the productivity under climate change?

DURUM WHEAT/ PASTA

All over the world, pasta is synonymous with of Italian cuisine. Despite being originally solely part of the Italian - and later European - culinary tradition, pasta has crossed international borders to become a very popular and, even staple, form of food in many parts of the globe.

MED-GOLD will combine different approaches to provide both seasonal forecasts and decadal predictions for durum wheat yield, risks of pests and diseases, as well as farmer-oriented decision process to define and apply better agro-management plans, like:

- Can optimal plan for fertilisation be developed?
- What information can be provided to select optimal variety and density?
- How can the supply chain be adapted to climate change to ensure sustainable production, quality and fair income?

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-8. MED-GOLD brochure

4.1.5. NEWLETTERS

The first newsletter will be published in December 2018 (Figure 4-8) and send by email to the already existing MED-GOLD community. The content is focused on "Perspectives of user engagement activities" and included different sections as:

- Project description
- Analysis of the experience accumulated in the focus groups and workshop of Work Package 2, 3 and 4 conducted between May and June 2018.
- Announcement of MED-GOLD partners' active participation in conferences, workshops and congresses in the coming months as novel aspects related to the project C&D activities.

Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, OLive and Durum wheat food systems

NEWSLETTER n° 1

November 2018

Dear Madame or Sir,

Thank you for joining the MED-GOLD community! Welcome.

As part of it, we are glad to send you our first newsletter. You will receive it regularly every 6 months. This will keep you updated on the latest research developments and the next activities organised by the project.

In the following sections of this first newsletter, you will find a summary of the first project steps undertaken and a list of announcements that can be of your interest. Enjoy!

Climate services for the Mediterranean agri-food system

Climate change is a global threat on food security and the Mediterranean region will be one of the most affected areas worldwide. MED-GOLD aims to develop climate services for the agriculture and food sectors impacted by climate variability and change. The project will provide novel pilot services to help farmers define both medium-term management strategies and long-term planning actions for three traditional Mediterranean crops (grapes, olives and durum wheat) and their associated products (wine, olive oil and pasta).

More information

First stage of the project: User needs first

Knowing user needs is paramount to develop climate services tailored to the MED-GOLD sectors of interest. Only this way climate services can be helpful and usable. With the objective to identify user needs in terms of weather and climate information, **focus groups** and **workshops** were conducted during May and June 2018.

Technical experts from the Portuguese winery Sogrape Vinhos S.A. participated in the **focus groups for grapes**, whereas participative workshops were organised for olive and durum wheat crops. Various agricultural technicians working in different departments of the Spanish cooperative Dcoop participated in the **olive workshop**, while the **durum wheat workshop** involved regional institutions, farmers, producer associations and elevators working with the Italian companies Barilla and Horta.

Photo by J. López, olive workshop

Announcements

User forum

Events with MED-GOLD presence

September 3-7, 2018

European Meteorological Society (EMS) » Budapest

The project coordinator (A. Dell'Aquila, ENEA) presented the contribution 'Voices from the field: climate prediction requirements in the agricultural sector from the MED-GOLD initiative'.

Source: S. Steiner and A. Ambros from Grafality for EMS. Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 license

September 17-21, 2018

MEDCLIVAR » Belgrade

Project partners NOA (C. Giannakopoulos) and JRC (M. Zampieri) presented contributions to this event, entitled 'Evaluation of various correction methods for Mediterranean agro-climate projections: results from the MED-GOLD project' and 'Climate impacts on Mediterranean crops, adaptation measures and the MED-GOLD project' respectively.

Photo by C. Giannakopoulos, MEDCLIVAR, venue

November 4-6, 2018

International DWV Congress (German Winegrowers Association) » Stuttgart

The MED-GOLD champion user for grapes and the wine sector, Sogrape (A. Grapa), was a speaker in the 63rd edition of this meeting.

Source: www.dew-congress.de

Upcoming Events

November 19-23, 2018

International OIV Congress of Vine and Wine » Uruguay

May 28-31, 2019

European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA) » Lisbon

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 776467

Image credits: World Food Systems, National Geographic Agency, Amy Ellis, ArtStation by and 20111
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Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-9. Some pictures of the MED-GOLD first newsletter

4.1.6. MED-GOLD INFO SHEET

"Climate services for grapes and the wine sector" was addressed in the first information sheet, which was published in 2018 (Figure 4-9). The objective has been to describe in a simple way the impact that climate services at different time scales may have on this sector. Moreover, and since the target group for this information is end-users that may not be familiar with this scope, a glossary has been included.

CLIMATE SERVICES FOR GRAPES AND THE WINE SECTOR

Grape and wine production is heavily affected by weather and climate, thereby is highly vulnerable to climate change. MED-GOLD will propose climate services deploying forecast information at the medium (next 6 months) and long-term (next 30 years). This information will be provided at higher spatial resolution than what is currently available. To provide the highest value for decision-making, the services will be co-developed with professional users from the sector.

Wine producers face diverse challenges affecting several decision processes in their business, such as strategic definitions, viticulture, oenological and stock management. Some examples are presented below to show how climate services - in this case, predictions of climate variables and bioclimatic indices - can improve decision-making and win over challenges posed by climate variability and climate change.

Time scale	Decision area	Challenge	MED-GOLD climate service	Benefits
Long-term (30 years)	Long-term strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purchase of new vineyards and/or selection of future new locations. Choice of grape varieties, rootstocks and vineyard design. Anticipation of needs to change wine style. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Precipitation Growing season average temperature Warm spell duration index Growing degree days Number of heat stress days Spring total precipitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indication of areas with suitable climate to meet production and quality goals for the next decades. Matching adequate grape varieties and rootstocks to expected climate. Identification of likely moment with adverse climate for current wine style.
Medium-term (6 months)	Viticulture management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better pruning and canopy management. Improve planning of treatments and harvest setting with higher accuracy. Better labour management, operational subcontracting and environmental protection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Precipitation Growing season average temperature Warm spell duration index Growing degree days Number of heat stress days Spring total precipitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Longer anticipation of best timing for vineyard operations. Identification of time periods with high-demand for labour and inputs. Schedule of best moments for treatments with higher temporal precision.
	Oenological management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better maturation control planning. Improve harvest efficiency. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of likely moments for veraison and harvest. Timely anticipation of adverse conditions.
	Stock management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve supplier negotiation. Better prices and supply chain. Marketing and promotions. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Anticipation of seasonal climate trends with adequate temporal and spatial resolution.

Planning of plant protection treatments

Several diseases affecting grapevines are favoured by specific climatic conditions. These diseases may be of fungal origin, namely downy and powdery mildew, among others, and of bacterial origin or caused by pests, namely insects. Fungal diseases occur when the plant, being a carrier, is exposed to favourable climatic conditions such as high humidity and mild-warm temperatures, which associated to poor aeration promote their development. When emerging at critical phenological stages, these diseases damage grapes, ultimately reducing yields and resulting in a loss of wine quality.

Currently, SOGRAPE (MED-GOLD's champion user for the wine sector) uses 4 to 5-day lead-time forecasts to schedule their spraying while avoiding product loss from subsequent rainfall. This anticipation of vineyard protection planning results in important, sustainable benefits. Medium-term decisions are currently undertaken with reference to past average conditions, both intuitively and using 30-year climate data series available from the national weather service.

Advantages of having access to medium-term (seasonal) climate predictions:

1. Efficient management of spraying against diseases, supporting vineyard development or inducing grapevine's resistance against humidity-driven diseases (fungal) in more sensitive phenological states.
2. Efficient stock management to be prepared in advance to avoid higher prices and stock disruptions.
3. Accurate setting of harvest dates, which is influenced by adverse conditions, namely pests risk.

Glossary

Climate services: transformation of climate-related data and other information into customized products such as trends, economic analysis, advice on best practices, and any other climate-related service liable to benefit that may be of use for the society

Weather forecasts: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables for the next hours and days (up to two weeks)

Climate predictions: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables that extend further into the future than weather forecasts, from months and seasons up to decades

Seasonal predictions: climate predictions for the next season. These predictions can be provided for the next 6 months

Climate projections: probabilistic forecasts of climate variables that extend even further into the future than climate predictions, from decades up to centuries

Growing season average temperature (GST): average of daily average temperatures between April 1st and October 31st (Northern Hemisphere)

Growing degree days (GDD): sum of daily differences between daily temperature averages and 10°C (vegetative growth minimum temperature) between April 1st and October 31st (Northern Hemisphere)

Spring total precipitation (SprP): total rainfall from April 21st to June 21st (Northern Hemisphere)

Number of heat stress days (SU35): annual count of days when daily maximum temperatures exceed 35°C

Warm spell duration index (WSDI): annual count of days with at least 6 consecutive days when the daily maximum temperature exceeds its 90th percentile

About MED-GOLD

MED-GOLD. Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional Mediterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems. It is a 4-year project contributing to make European agriculture and food systems more resilient, sustainable and efficient in the face of climate change by using climate services to minimize climate-driven risks/costs and seize opportunities for added value

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 776467

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-10. Grape/Wine info sheet

In the next months, other infosheet will per produced for the other sectors of interest and for other general purposes.

4.1.7. MED-GOLD WEBINAR

The first webinar was performed the 15th January of 2019 entitled "Climate services as drivers of value into the Mediterranean wine sector". The language used was Portuguese since it was focus on grape-wine sector which in MED-GOLD is led by a pilot in Portugal.

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-11. **MED-GOLD webinar focus on grape-wine.**

4.1.8. MED-GOLD EVENTS

Table 4-1 summarizes the events that have been organized by different partners for attendees of both internal and external project members. Photographs from some of the events are shown in Figure 4-10.

Table 4-1. List of MED-GOLD events performed.

ID	Partner' organiser	Name of the event	Date of the event	Location of the event (city, country)	Description of the event	N° of attendees	Evaluation sheet results
1	ENEA	Kick off meeting	11 th -12 th of December 2017	Roma (IT)	First meeting of all MED-GOLD partners. Definition of the project plan.	31 participants (partners members)	N/A
2	SOGRAPE	Wine/grape focus group	3 rd -4 th of May 2018	Porto (Portugal)	Workshop about identifying what wine companies need to know about the future weather and climate and how they want to receive this information.	12 technical experts working in SOGRAPE	Average age: 52 years-old Gender: 100% males Profile. Technician General satisfaction: 8.8 Duration: 7.3 Organization: 8.5 Material provided: 8.25 Location: 8.754 Speaker skills: 9.22 Usefulness of climate services: 9.4
3	HORTA	Durum wheat/pasta workshop	15 th -16 th of May 2018	Ravenna (IT)	An institutional meeting to ascertain the key operational and strategic decision-making processes that could potentially benefit from the use of seasonal climate forecasts, long-term climate change projection. Workshop to acknowledge current use and potential improvement of the DSS system in durum wheat farms.	11 technical experts from Italian political institutions, breeding, academic world and stocks exchange markets. 16 participants among durum wheat farmers, producer's association and elevators across different Italian regions	Average age: 52 years-old Gender: 40% females / 60% male Profile. Technician General satisfaction: 8.8 Duration: 7.6 Organization: 8.8 Material provided: 7.4 Location: 9 Speaker skills: 8.8 Usefulness of climate services: 9.6

ID	Partner' organiser	Name of the event	Date of the event	Location of the event (city, country)	Description of the event	N° of attendees	Evaluation sheet results
4	DCOOP	Olive/olive oil workshop	12 th of June 2018	Antequera (SP)	Workshop aimed to identify the needs of the users from the olive oil sector across the whole value chain and understand what kind of climate information could be of benefit to them.	20 agricultural engineers from DCOOP's Technical Field Department	Average age: 39 years-old Gender: 27% females / 73% males Profile. Technician General satisfaction: 7.3 Duration: 6.6 Organization: 7.7 Material provided: 7.6 Location: 8.3 Speaker skills: 7.7 Usefulness of climate services: 8.4
5	SOGRAPE	Stakeholder workshop / presentation	29 th of October	Porto (Portugal)	MED-GOLD presentation about the objectives of the project and potentials for the wine sector	18 participants from the Portuguese wine sector and national authorities.	N/A
6	SOGRAPE	1 st General Assembly	29 th -31 st of October 2018	Porto (Portugal)	Review project status after one year of project's life, identify deviations and agreed an action plan for the next upcoming year.	29 participants (partners and Advisory Board members)	Average age: 39 years-old Gender: 43.75% females / 56.25% males Profile. Technician / Academia General satisfaction: 8.7 Duration: 8.7 Organization: 8.8 Material provided: 8.8 Location: 9.3 Speaker skills: 9.1

In general, most of the participants agreed of the great usefulness of climate services in their respectively sectors. Regarding the organization of the sessions, more attention needs to be paid to the duration and materials provided, although in general they were adequate.

During 2019, several focus groups for each sector has been performed. They will detailed describe in the next report about C&D activities.

Figure Errore. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-12. **Photographs of the events.**

4.1.9. PRESS RELEASES & NEWS

Table 4-2. List of MED-GOLD press releases and news published by project partners during the first year (M1-M18) of MED-GOLD

ID	Partner involved	Date	Target group	Region of interest	Title	Site / Media	Link
1	ENEA	05/01/2018	PR&GP	IT	Trasformare le informazioni legate al clima in valore aggiunto per i sistemi agroalimentari mediterranei tradizionali vite, olivo e grano duro	ENEA website	click here
2	ENEA	18/01/2018	PR&GP	IT	Ambiente: ENEA con Barilla e altri big per salvare pasta, olio d'oliva e vino dall'impatto dei cambiamenti climatici	ENEA website	click here
3	ENEA	18/01/2018	PR&GP	IT	Climate change vs olio, pasta e vino: alleanza scienza-imprese per difenderli	ADNKRONOS website	click here
4	ENEA	18/01/2018	GP	IT	Climate change vs olio, pasta e vino. Alleanza scienza-imprese per difenderli	Libero Quotidian website	click here
5	ENEA	18/01/2018	GP	IT	Med-Gold, un progetto per salvare pasta, olio e vino dai cambiamenti climatici	Alternativa Sostenibile website	click here
6	ENEA	18/01/2018	GP	IT	Enea e imprese insieme per salvare pasta, olio e vino dal cambiamento climatico	Help Consumatori website	click here
7	ENEA	18/01/2018	GP	IT	Clima: Enea con Barilla e big per salvare pasta, olio e vino	Agenzia ANSA website	click here
8	ENEA	18/01/2018	GP	IT	Pasta, olio d'oliva e vino: per salvare le eccellenze dell'agroalimentare Mediterraneo dall'impatto dei cambiamenti climatici nasce "MED-GOLD - oro del Mediterraneo", un'alleanza fra scienziati e grandi imprese, con Barilla, DCOOP e Sogrape Vinhos	Wine News website	click here
9	ENEA	18/01/2018	GP	IT	Ricerca scientifica italiana nel mondo - agroalimentare - ENEA coordina MED GOLD progetto europeo per salvare grano(Italia) olio(Spagna) e vino (Portogallo) dai cambiamenti climatici	Italian Network website	click here
10	ENEA	19/01/2018	GP	IT	Cibo: nasce alleanza europea per proteggere vite, olivo e grano duro	First online website	click here
11	ENEA	19/01/2018	GP	IT	Med-Gold per salvare grano, vite e olivo da impatto cambio clima	Askaneews website	click here
12	ENEA	19/01/2018	GP	IT	MED-GOLD protegge olio, vino e pasta dai cambiamenti climatici	Corriere nazionale website	click here
13	ENEA	19/01/2018	GP	IT	MED-GOLD1, 'Oro del Mediterraneo', il progetto europeo di ricerca per vite, olivo e grano duro	Vivavoce website	click here
14	ENEA	20/01/2018	GP	IT	Riscaldamento climatico. Ecco i nuovi studi (e le nuove contromisure)	Il sole 24 ore website	click here
15	ENEA	20/01/2018	GP	IT	Barilla ed Enea: progetto per salvare grano, vino e olio da cambiamenti climatici	Parma quotidiano website	click here
16	ENEA	30/01/2018	PR&GP	GLOBAL	Progetto MED-GOLD	ENEA website	click here
17	GMV	30/01/2018	PR&GP	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD	GMV website	click here
18	ENEA	07/02/2018	PR&GP	IT	Quali impatti per l'Italia e la sua agricoltura con il clima del futuro?	Qual Energia website	click here
19	BSC	14/02/2018	INSTITUTION S	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD – Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional MEDiterranean Grape, Olive and Durum wheat food systems	Climate Europe website	click here

ID	Partner involved	Date	Target group	Region of interest	Title	Site / Media	Link
20	UMNG	15/03/2018	Grape	PT	Sogrape aposta em agricultura climaticamente inteligente	SOGRAPE VINHOS website	click here
21	SOGRAPE	15/03/2018	Grape	PT	SOGRAPE INTEGRA PROJETO DE PESQUISA E INOVAÇÃO CLIMÁTICA	Ambiente Magazine website	click here
22	SOGRAPE	16/03/2018	Grape	PT	Projeto MED-GOLD cria ferramentas climatológicas para culturas mediterrânicas	Agronegocios website	click here
23	ENEA	23-04-2018	GP	IT	L'importanza dei big data e degli small data nell'agricoltura di precisione	Audible website	click here
24	BSC	09/05/2018	Climate	GLOBAL	BSC: Helping to ensure the future of the Mediterranean diet	BSC website	click here
25	BSC	09/05/2018	Grape	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD focus groups held at SOGRAPE	MED-GOLD website	click here
26	BSC	09/05/2018	PR&GP	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD: Helping to ensure the future of the Mediterranean diet	MED-GOLD website	click here
27	BSC	14/05/2018	Climate	GLOBAL	BSC Powers Climate Services for Agriculture in Europe	Insice HPC website	click here
28	BSC	14/05/2018	PR&GP	GLOBAL	BSC Participating in the MED-GOLD Mediterranean Food Production Project	HPC wine magazine	click here
29	BSC	14/05/2018	PR&GP	SP	Investigan para que cambio climático no merme productos de dieta mediterránea	La Vanguardia website	click here
30	BSC	14/05/2018	PR&GP	SP	El BSC participa en MED-GOLD para optimizar la producción de la uva, el aceite de oliva y el trigo	CIO SPAIN website	click here
31	BSC	14/05/2018	Climate	SP	Un mapa meteorològic per salvar les collites de vi, oli i blat	ARA.CAT website	click here
32	BSC	15/05/2018	GP	SP	Wine production in the Pyrenees and hungry caribous and why it matters	MED-GOLD website	click here
33	DCOOP	13/06/2018	GP - Olive	SP	Dcoop participa en un proyecto europeo para diseñar servicios climáticos para el olivar	Diariosur website	click here
34	GMV	20/06/2018	GP	SP	MED-GOLD hacia el futuro de la agricultura sostenible y eficiente	GMV website	click here
35	NOA	05/07/2018	PR&GP	GR	MED-GOLD, ένα τετραετές πρόγραμμα σε αναζήτηση της χρυσής τομής για μία φιλική προς το κλίμα γεωργία στη Μεσόγειο	NOA website	click here
36	ENEA	19/07/2018	Climate	IT	Sicilia: progetto Med-Gold per rispondere ai cambiamenti climatici	Fresh Plaza website	click here
37	DCOOP	30/07/2018	Olive	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD workshop on olive at DCOOP	MED-GOLD website	click here
38	SOGRAPE	25/10/2018	GP	PT	Estudar o impacto das alterações climáticas na agricultura	Industria & Ambiente website	click here
39	ENEA	26/10/2018	GP	IT	Climate change e agricoltura: ENEA coordina il progetto MED-GOLD	Alimentazione Rinnovabili website	click here
40	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Portugal integra projeto europeu sobre ameaças climáticas ao setor do vinho	Diario de Noticias website	click here
41	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Vinho português entra em projeto europeu sobre ameaças climáticas	Economia online website	click

ID	Partner involved	Date	Target group	Region of interest	Title	Site / Media	Link
42	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Portugal integra projeto europeu sobre ameaças climáticas ao setor do vinho	Ominho website	click here
43	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Portugal integra projeto sobre ameaças climáticas ao setor do vinho	Economia Ao Minuto website	click here
44	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Vinho português entra em projeto europeu sobre ameaças climáticas	SAPO website	click here
45	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Portugal integra projeto europeu sobre ameaças climáticas ao setor do vinho	SIC Noticias website	click here
46	SOGRAPE	29/10/2018	GP	PT	Portugal integra projeto europeu sobre ameaças climáticas ao setor do vinho	TSF Radio website	click here
47	SOGRAPE	30/10/2018	GP	PT	Ameaças climáticas a setores agrícolas	JM Magazine website	click here
48	BSC	05/11/2018	GP	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD European project on climate threats to the agricultural sector	MED-GOLD Website	click here
49	GMV	07/11/2018	GP	GLOBAL	The H2020 MED-GOLD project holds its first general assembly	GMV website	click here
50	SOGRAPE	20/11/2018	GP	PT	Sogrape recebe 1.ª assembleia-geral do projecto europeu Med-Gold em Vila Nova de Gaia	Agriculturaemar website	click here
51	SOGRAPE	22/01/2018	GP	PT	Sogrape acolheu assembleia-geral do projecto europeu MED-GOLD	FIF revista	click here
52	BSC	01/12/2018	GP	GLOBAL	1st MED-GOLD Newsletter	MED-GOLD website	click here
53	SOGRAPE	01/01/2019	Grape	GLOBAL	MED- GOLD: prever o clima para melhorar a gestão vitivinícola	Sogrape website	click here
54	ENEA/BSC	13/02/2019	GP	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD workshop on the user perspective of seasonal forecasts	MED-GOLD website	click here
55	SOGRAPE	04/03/2019	Grape	GLOBAL	Project MED-GOLD in Portuguese TV (RTP)	Portuguese television	click here
56	ENEA	13/03/2019	GP	GOBAL	One year of MED-GOLD: Interview with the coordinators	MED-GOLD website	click here
57	SOGRAPE	15/03/2019	Grape	GLOBAL	Fighting climate change in the wine sector (PT)	Agronegocio website	click here
58	DCOOP	09/05/2019	Olive	SP	Dcoop celebra un Grupo Focal para evaluar la herramienta para el olivar diseñada por MED-GOLD	Oleum Xauen website	click here
59	DCOOP	09/05/2019	Olive	SP	Dcoop evalúa la herramienta para el olivar diseñada por el proyecto europeo MED-GOLD	Mercacei website	click here
60	DCOOP	10/05/2019	Olive	SP	Dcoop celebra un Grupo Focal para evaluar la herramienta para el olivar diseñada por Med-Gold	20 minutes magazine	click here
61	DCOOP	10/05/2019	Olive	SP	Dcoop participa en el diseño de una herramienta para predecir la evolución de la plaga de la mosca del olivo	Diario Sur newspaper	click here
62	DCOOP	10/05/2019	Olive	SP	Dcoop colabora en el proyecto MED-GOLD	Olimerca website	click here

4.1.10. PARTICIPATION IN CONFERENCES, WORKSHOPS AND EVENTS

Table 4-3. List of events in which MED-GOLD partners have participated during 2018-2019

ID	Partner involved	Event contribution	Date	Sector involved	Target group	Region of interest	Title	Link
1	DCOOP	CONFERENCE POSTER	13/03/2018	OLIVE	GP	SP	ANDALUCIA DIGITAL WEEK 2018	click here
2	CREA	CONFERENCE	03/04/2018	OLIVE	PR	GLOBAL	FAO International agroecology conference	click here
3	ENEA	CONFERENCE	13/04/2018	ALL	PR	EUROPE	EGU Annual Meeting 2018:	click here
4	BSC	CONFERENCE	13/04/2018	ALL	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	European Geosciences Union (EGU) conference. Vienna, Austria.	click here
5	ENEA	WORKSHOP	04/05/2018	ALL	PR&GP	GLOBAL	INTERNATIONAL AGROECOLOGY SHORT COURSE, 2-5 May 2018, Polvese Island, Trasimeno Lake, Italy	click here
6	DCOOP	CONFERENCE	10/05/2018	OLIVE	END-USERS	SP	Instituto de la Grasa meeting, 2018	click here
7	CREA	CONFERENCE	27/05/2018	OLIVE	GP	GLOBAL	4th European Agroforestry Conference	click here
8	ENEA	MEETING	29/05/2018	CLIMATE	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	GA CLARA PROJECT	click here
9	ENEA	WORKSHOP	29/05/2018	DURUM WHEAT	PR	IT	MED-GOLD focus groups held at HORTA	click here
10	BSC	CONFERENCE	30/05/2018	ALL	PR&GP	SP	VII Jornades Ambientals 2018	click here
11	BSC	WORKSHOP	01/06/2018	CLIMATE	PR&GP	GLOBAL	Second WMO Workshop on Operational Climate Prediction	click here
12	SOGRAPE	CONFERENCE	22/06/2018	GRAPE	ACADEMIA	GLOBAL	XII Congreso Internacional sobre el Terroir	click here
13	ENEA	CONFERENCE	03/09/2018	ALL	PR	EUROPE	European Meteorological Society Annual Meeting 2018	click here
14	GMV	MEETING	12/09/2018	CLIMATE	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	Participation on the 1st meeting of CS project under Climateurope	
15	NOA	CONFERENCE	20/09/2018	OLIVE	ACADEMIA	SP	MEDCLIVAR 2018 conference. Serbia, Belgrade	click here
16	BSC	CONFERENCE	16/10/2018	GRAPE	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	11 Congreso internacional Asociación Española de Climatología, Cartagena Spain 17-19 October 2018	click here
17	SOGRAPE / BSC	MEETING	17/10/2018	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	Climateurope Festival 2018	click here
18	BSC	CONFERENCE	19/10/2018	GRAPE	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	ENSO 2018 meeting, Climate Services stage, Guayaquil 16-18 October 2018	click here
19	SOGRAPE	CONFERENCE	19/11/2018	GRAPE	INSTITUTIONS	GLOBAL	41st. World Congress of Vine and Wine	click here
20	SOGRAPE	CONFERENCE	22/11/2018	CLIMATE	PR&GP	PT	CLIMA 2018 - Congresso Nacional sobre Alterações Climáticas	click here
21	ENEA	CONFERENCE	27/11/2018	GRAPE	GP	GLOBAL	MED-GOLD project presentation at the 10th World Bulk Wine Exhibition in Amsterdam, The Netherlands	click here

22	UNIVLEEDS	WORKSHOP	12/12/2018	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	Agrisource European Workshop in Paris	click here
23	SOGRAPE	WORKSHOP	08/02/2019	ALL	GP	PORTUGAL	Presentation «We can't trust in our grandfathers anymore?» - slide about MED-GOLD	click here
ID	Partner involved	Event contribution	Date	Sector involved	Target group	Region of interest	Title	Link
24	SOGRAPE	CONFERENCE	06/03/2019	GRAPE	GP	GLOBAL	Presentation «Vineyards responses around the world»	click here
25	BSC	WORKSHOP	19/03/2019	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	GLOBAL	Trainer in workshop on communication, visualisation and user engagement within the COST inDust project, Bucharest (RO)	click here
26	BSC	WORKSHOP	09/04/2019	ALL	ACADEMIA	GLOBAL	Presentation in workshop on climate change impact on agriculture, Barcelona	click here
27	ENEA	CONFERENCE	10/04/2019	ALL	ACADEMIA	EUROPE	Oral presentation at European Geophysical Union General Assembly 2019, Vienna, Austria, 7-12 April 2019. see Geophysical Research Abstracts, 21: EGU2019-13677. https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU2019/EGU2019-13677.pdf	click here
28	ENEA/BEET OBIT	MEETING	08/05/2019	ALL	INSTITUTIONS	EUROPE	Talk in ECMWF to present MED-GOLD and ICT platform	
29	SOGRAPE	CONFERENCE	13/05/2019	GRAPE	ACADEMIA	GLOBAL	Oral presentation at the Oenoviti Symposium, Athens, Greece	click here

4.1.11. LINKS WITH OTHER INITIATIVES

Dissemination synergies with other EU initiatives such as Climate-KIC, JPI Climate, FACE-JPI, JPI Water and related ERA-NET (e.g. ERA-NET on Climate Services) as well as clustering with other climate service related EC funded projects via H2020 or other complementary programmes (i.e. LIFE, Copernicus, PRIMA, etc.) has been explored during this first project life. Deliverable 6.1 “Climate Related Initiatives Interactions Report n.1” summarised those interactions [RD.4].

4.1.12. MED-GOLD GAZETTE

Internal blog where relevant events in the life of MED-GOLD project are summarised to help partners to stay on the trail (Figure 4-11). It is published quarterly.

Figure Error. Per applicare Titolo 1 al testo da visualizzare in questo punto, utilizzare la scheda Home.-13. MED-GOLD GAZETTE on the project wiki.

5. CONCLUSIONS

During the first year (M1-M12) of MED-GOLD, a number of steps have been performed in order to design and structure the approach to communication and dissemination approach. A significant effort has been performed on visual identify and MED-GOLD community engagement. A revision of this document has been performed on M18.

Most of the activities have been focus on communicating project objective and disseminating the expected MED-GOLD's results for engaging stakeholders. Table below shows current figures and status based on the above results:

Table 5-1. List of events in which MED-GOLD

Metrics	Figure
Number of organized workshops	9
Average number of participants in events	19
Number of MED-GOLD community members	58
Number of info sheets published	1
Number of newsletters	1
Number of publications in media	62
Number of presentations in conferences, meetings and congresses	20
Initiatives contacted	41
Date: 28 th May of 2019	

More attention should be sought in the following years of the MED-GOLD project to increase the impact and the number of community members once that the infrastructure and content has been generated. MED-GOLD consortium is working on new materials based on the advances performed for the target audiences and increase the project impact.

END OF DOCUMENT

